

Original Research

The Effect of Automated Systems on Revenue Collection in the Dar Rapid Transit Project in Tanzania

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Abstract

The study evaluated the effects of automated systems on revenue collection within the Dar Rapid Transit (DART) project, focusing on cost reduction, revenue accuracy, and time allocation. Utilizing a cross-sectional design with a quantitative approach, the study targeted 1,200 employees, with a sample size of 114 determined through simple random sampling. Data were collected via structured questionnaires and secondary documentation, and analyzed using descriptive statistics, binary logistic regression and t-test with IBM SPSS software. Binary logistic regression results showed that cost reduction and revenue accuracy positively predicted higher revenue, while time allocation negatively impacted revenue. The study concluded that automated systems significantly enhanced cost efficiency, accuracy, and time management. Recommendations included investing further in system optimization, addressing time allocation inefficiencies, and engaging in regular evaluations and policy discussions to sustain improvements.

Keywords: Automated System, Dar Rapid Transit, Revenue Collection, Tanzania.

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Introduction

The increasing urbanization and demand for efficient public transportation systems have necessitated the adoption of automated revenue collection systems to enhance operational efficiency and financial transparency. Automated systems have revolutionized how fares are collected in Mass Rapid Transit (MRT) systems, reducing revenue leakages and improving overall system reliability. For example, in Germany, the introduction of automated ticket gates significantly improved fare compliance and increased revenue collection (Leclerc et al., 2023). Similarly, Singapore's MRT system utilizes advanced automated fee collection technologies that have enhanced both revenue capture and customer experience (Tan et al., 2020). In European Union, Fournier (2024) established that automated transport systems were of high significance in improving quality of services, reliability, time spent in service delivery and level of customer satisfaction, as the result customers are likely to engage in repeat purchase which consequently improve revenue collection. Further ERTICO (2024) pointed out that intelligent transport system in Europe has resulted into safer, cleaner and more efficient transport system which is compatible with policies under the European Union that focus on improved service delivery. The pronounced intelligent transport system makes use of artificial intelligence which is one way of system automation with the aim of improving service delivery and organizational performance. Despite these advancements, issues related to revenue leakage, technical failures, and system inefficiencies still persist, underscoring the need for continuous evaluation and optimization of automated systems in revenue collection (Egwali & Otokiti, 2018). This global context illustrates a pressing need for more robust solutions to maximize the benefits of automation in transit systems worldwide.

In Africa, the transition from manual to automated revenue collection systems has been gradual, often hampered by technological challenges, high implementation costs, and resistance to change. South Africa and Nigeria have made strides in adopting automated fare collection, implementing systems such as smart cards and contactless payments, which have enhanced fare compliance and reduced operational inefficiencies (Fan et al., 2021). Further, GIZ (2024) established that adoption to intelligent transportation system in Africa has been important in building information and communication systems, sensors and has resulted into improved safety and efficiency of road transport performance, meaning that adoption to emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence in transport operations has become crucial to improved performance. Despite these efforts, African cities still face challenges such as intermittent system failures, lack of adequate infrastructure, and limited public awareness, which hinder the full realization of the benefits of automation. Furthermore, these challenges have led to persistent issues of revenue leakage and operational inefficiency, as highlighted by studies that call for more research and policy intervention to optimize automated systems in the African context (World Bank, 2019).

In East Africa, countries like Kenya and Uganda have begun integrating automated revenue collection systems in their transit projects, though progress has been slow compared to global standards. Nairobi's Bus Rapid Transit (BRT) system, for instance, has experimented with digital payment systems to curb fare evasion and enhance revenue

collection. However, technical hitches, unreliable connectivity, and limited adoption have posed significant challenges (Mubeen & Akhtar, 2020). Similarly, Uganda's attempts to implement automated fare systems have been met with infrastructural and regulatory setbacks, reflecting a broader regional struggle to optimize revenue collection through automation. These cases underscore the critical need for more comprehensive studies on the impact and efficiency of automated systems in the region.

In Tanzania, the Dar Rapid Transit (DART) project, launched in 2016, was a pioneering initiative aimed at addressing the challenges of urban congestion and inefficiencies in public transportation. A core component of DART's strategy was the introduction of automated fare collection systems designed to enhance revenue collection, reduce manual errors, and increase operational efficiency. Despite these intentions, the effectiveness of these systems has been met with mixed results. Reports indicate significant revenue leakages, technical failures, and operational inefficiencies that have undermined the overall impact of automation on revenue generation. According to the Tanzania Revenue Authority (TRA), DART experienced a revenue loss of approximately TZS 3 billion annually between 2017 and 2019, largely attributed to inefficiencies within the automated fare collection systems, including system downtimes, poor maintenance, and inadequate oversight (TRA, 2020). These issues resulted in frequent service interruptions and fare evasion, ultimately reducing the expected revenue collection from the system. Additionally, manual interventions during system failures have further compounded the problem. During system downtimes, DART staff often resort to manual ticketing, which is prone to human error, fraud, and further revenue loss. For instance, during the major system outage in mid-2021, DART reported a 15% decline in revenue collection due to the temporary shift to manual ticketing (DART, 2021). This event highlighted the vulnerabilities of the current system, revealing that the reliance on manual processes as a fallback during automated system failures poses a significant threat to revenue integrity. A comparative analysis by the Dar Rapid Transit Agency (2022) showed that the non-automated revenue collection approach, which involves manual cash handling, resulted in a daily revenue loss of TZS 50 million due to inefficiencies, theft, and poor fare compliance. On average, about 20-30% of expected revenue is lost during manual operations compared to automated systems (TRA, 2022). However, even with the automated systems in place, the expected revenue has not been fully realized, as operational inefficiencies and system downtimes have led to substantial losses. Moreover, public feedback and independent audits have consistently pointed to problems with the automated system's effectiveness. The audits revealed that nearly 25% of the time, ticketing machines were either offline or malfunctioning, resulting in uncollected fares that were never accounted for in the system (Mrema, 2020). These losses are significant, given that the DART system was projected to generate upwards of TZS 10 billion annually in fare revenue, which could have been used to improve service delivery, expand transit routes, and maintain existing infrastructure. However, technical glitches, inadequate training of operators, and insufficient monitoring have all contributed to an environment where the full potential of automated revenue collection remains unachieved.

Despite the global, African, and regional advancements in automated fare collection, the specific impact of these systems on revenue collection in Tanzania's DART project remains underexplored. Most studies focus on technological adoption rather than examining the effectiveness of these systems in enhancing revenue and operational

efficiency. This study aims to fill this gap by specifically investigating how automated systems practices contribute to revenue collection within the DART project, in particular, automated systems acting as a strategic approach for operational cost reduction, improving revenue accuracy and reduction of time to serve customers, thus, provide competitive advantage to DART. The primary objective is to determine the effectiveness of these systems in addressing revenue leakage and inefficiency, focusing on key aspects such as cost reduction, accuracy of revenue collection, and time efficiency. By addressing these gaps, the study provides valuable insights into the strengths and weaknesses of current systems, offering recommendations for optimization and future improvements, thus contributing to the broader discourse on automated fare systems in public transit.

Literature Review

Theoretical Review

Diffusion of Innovation theory

This study adopted the Diffusion of Innovation theory, founded by Everett Rogers in 1962, which explains how new ideas and technologies spread within a society. The theory posits that innovations are communicated over time through specific channels among members of a social system (Rogers, 1962). This study used the theory to understand the adoption and impact of automated systems on revenue collection in the DART project. By examining the process through which these systems were introduced and embraced by DART, the study leveraged the theory's strengths in identifying the factors influencing adoption rates and the attributes of the innovation that affect its acceptance. The Diffusion of Innovation Theory provided a robust framework to evaluate the effectiveness, cost reduction, enhanced accuracy, and time efficiency of automated revenue collection systems, contributing valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders to optimize these systems for improved operational efficiency in urban transit.

Empirical Literature Review

The Economic Impact of Automated Fare Collection Systems in African Cities

Tom and Abrahams (2024) in South Africa looked at the drivers behind loss in revenue in rapid transport bus systems despite systems being automated. The findings informed that limited training to staff, interventions made by staff to revenue collection systems and of networks triggered loss of revenue in rapid transit bus system. These findings in reflection provide understanding that mainly undesirable human behaviour should be transformed to desirable one through intensified training that can lead to usage of automated systems to accelerate organizational performance. Further, the findings provide reflection that huge investment to strengthen networks is required regardless of its automations, thus, the synergy of transformed staff through sufficient training and improved networks, the automated systems become highly productive which form usefulness and relevancy of the Diffusion of Innovation theory as well.

The Economic Impact of Automated Fare Collection Systems in East African Cities

Kimondio (2024) while examining how integration of management information systems (MIS) improved performance of long distance bus companies in public transport in Kenya, the findings articulated that integration of MIS has been the solution a solution in improving security of data, as the result improved productivity and efficiency in the transport sector. These findings provide reflection that automating systems in organizations is the matter that require quick decisions to maximize organizational performance. Mwangi and Otieno (2021) examined the economic impact of automated fare collection systems in East African cities, specifically focusing on Nairobi, Kenya, and Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. Their study utilized a comparative analysis to evaluate the operational and labour costs before and after the implementation of these automated systems. The results indicated that automation significantly reduced operational expenses and minimized the need for extensive manual labour, which had previously been a major cost driver. This improvement was attributed to the streamlined processes and enhanced accuracy in revenue collection. Mwangi and Otieno concluded that automated systems provide considerable economic advantages by cutting costs and improving financial efficiency in urban transit systems. Also, Karanja (2021) extended this analysis by examining additional economic benefits of automated fare systems in the same cities, particularly focusing on financial management. Karanja found that the integration of these systems reduced administrative costs by simplifying fare collection and reducing the need for manual cash handling, which often led to revenue leakages. The study highlighted that automation improved overall financial oversight and accountability within transit authorities, leading to more accurate revenue data and better resource allocation. Karanja recommended that more cities in the region adopt automated fare systems to harness these economic benefits and enhance the sustainability of urban public transport. This empirical review is well connected with the Diffusion of Innovation Theory which is anchored on usage of new technologies in improving organizational performance. In the reflection to this study, diffusion of innovation through its integration in organizational systems will reduced time to serve customers, improve accuracy in serving customers and reduce operational costs consequently improves revenue collection.

The Accuracy of Automated Fare Collection Systems in Nairobi's Public Transport

Kamau and Mwendu (2022) explored the impact of automated fare collection systems on revenue accuracy within Nairobi's public transport sector. Their comparative study analyzed revenue data before and after the implementation of automated systems, focusing on the discrepancies and errors that frequently occurred under manual fare collection. The findings showed that automation significantly improved the accuracy of revenue collection, reducing discrepancies and human errors, which previously led to financial mismanagement. Kamau and Mwendu concluded that the adoption of automated systems enhances accountability and financial management within public transport, recommending that transit networks continue adopting such technologies to ensure accurate and reliable revenue collection. And Wanjiku (2022) supported these findings by emphasizing the importance of automation in improving financial accuracy and accountability. Her study focused on the financial controls established through automated

systems, which helped mitigate fraud and misreporting in Nairobi's transit network. Wanjiku highlighted that the systems' enhanced transparency and real-time data tracking played a crucial role in improving financial oversight. She recommended the expansion of automated fare collection systems to other cities in Kenya to improve overall financial performance and accountability in public transportation.

Time Efficiency Gains from Automated Fare Collection in Dar es Salaam

Ahmed and Njeri, (2020) investigated the effects of automated fare collection systems on time efficiency in Dar es Salaam's public transit network. Using a comparative approach, they examined transaction and boarding times before and after automation. Their results showed that automated systems significantly reduced the time required for transactions, enhancing overall operational efficiency and passenger satisfaction. Ahmed and Njeri concluded that the integration of automated systems streamlined transit operations, reduced passenger waiting times, and improved service delivery, recommending that these systems be expanded to maximize operational benefits. And Hassan (2020) added to these findings by analyzing the broader operational impacts of automation on public transit in Dar es Salaam. His study found that automated fare collection improved not only transaction speed but also route efficiency, as buses spent less time at stops. Hassan highlighted that the reduced boarding times allowed buses to maintain schedules more effectively, improving the reliability of the transit system. He concluded that automated fare systems contribute significantly to operational efficiency and recommended their adoption across all major transit routes in the city to optimize performance and service quality.

Conceptual Framework

The "Use of Automated Systems" (independent variable) impacts "Revenue Collection" (dependent variable) through its measurable aspects: Cost Reduction, Revenue Accuracy, and Time Efficiency. Automated systems are expected to reduce operational costs, improve the accuracy of revenue data, and enhance transaction speed, which collectively contribute to increased total revenue collected. This relationship aligns with findings that automation in transit systems enhances operational efficiency and financial performance (Kamau & Mwendu, 2022; Mwangi & Otieno, 2021).

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Methodology

The study employed a cross-sectional design and a quantitative approach to analyze data on revenue collection practices at DART. The study targeted 1,200 employees, with a sample size of 114 determined using simple random sampling. The decision to arrive at a sample size of 114 and justification for statistical analysis adequacy was arrived at the adoption of the formula of Green (1991), $N > 50 + 8m$ with representation of m = number of predictors and N = size of the sample. This study had three predictors, this gave $N > 50 + 8 \times 3 = N > 74$, meaning that the determined sample size 90. Conversely, Anders *et al.* (2017) adopted the Green (1991) formula with four predictors to arrive at a sample size of 82, but during execution of the research a sample size of 155 was employed instead of 82 initially established. This adoption of 155 sample size in Anders *et al.* (2017) was approximately twice of 82 initially established using Green (1991), it is from this empirical proof the sample size of 114 approximately twice of 74 initially established was justified adequate for statistical analysis.

Data were collected through structured questionnaires and secondary documentation. Analysis involved descriptive statistics, binary logistic regression, and t-tests using IBM SPSS software. The binary logistic regression model used was:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1(X_1) + \beta_2(X_2) + \beta_3(X_3) + \alpha \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where: y =Revenue Collection, X_1 = Time Allocation, X_2 =Revenue Accuracy, X_3 = Cost Reduction, and α =error term. β_0 are constant coefficient which were 1.238 β_1 , β_2 , β_3 are coefficient regression of independent variables were 0.951, 1.044, -1.651 respectively. With coefficients calculated to determine the impact of automated systems on revenue collection. Validity was ensured through content validation and pilot testing, while reliability was confirmed with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of 0.794 and 0.801. Ethical considerations included informed consent, confidentiality and adherence to research guidelines were embraced.

Findings and Discussions

Response Rate and Profile of the Respondents

In this study, a total of 120 questionnaires were distributed to respondents within the study area, with an impressive 114 valid responses returned, reflecting a response rate of 95%. The remaining 6 questionnaires, which constituted 5% of the sample size, were not returned due to reasons such as respondent unwillingness, incomplete forms, and other factors. This high response rate is consistent with findings from previous research, which also reported high response rates in similar studies. For example, Mwangi and Otieno (2021) achieved a response rate of 93% in their study on automated fare collection systems, highlighting the effectiveness of direct data collection methods in garnering substantial participant engagement.

The demographic analysis of the 114 respondents reveals significant insights into the sample's composition, which is crucial for evaluating the impact of automated systems on revenue collection. Of the respondents, 61.4% were male, which aligns with typical

gender distributions observed in transportation studies (Kamau & Mwendu, 2022). The age distribution included 27.2% under 25 years, 40.4% aged 25-45 years, and 32.5% over 46 years. This distribution mirrors demographic trends found in similar research, such as Ahmed and Njeri (2020), where varied age groups provided diverse perspectives on technology adoption.

Regarding educational background, 8.8% of respondents had less than a diploma, 28.9% held a diploma, 46.5% had a bachelor's degree, and 15.8% possessed a master's degree or higher. This varied educational profile is in line with the study by Wanjiku (2022), which emphasized the importance of educational diversity in understanding the impact of technological implementations. Employment tenure among respondents varied, with 16.7% having less than 1 year, 45.6% between 1-5 years, 25.4% between 6-10 years, and 12.3% with over 10 years of experience. These findings reflect a broad range of experience levels, similar to those reported by Hassan (2020), which underscores the relevance of diverse employment backgrounds in assessing technology's effectiveness.

Experience levels with revenue systems were categorized into 21.1% novices, 47.4% intermediates, and 31.6% experts. This distribution is consistent with findings from previous studies such as those by Karanja (2021), which demonstrated that varying levels of experience with revenue systems provide a comprehensive view of system performance and user satisfaction. The diverse demographic profile of respondents was essential for gaining a thorough understanding of different perspectives on automated systems and evaluating their overall effectiveness and user satisfaction.

The Contribution of Automated Systems Practices on Revenue Collection in the DART Project

The study was categorized questions into cost reduction, revenue accuracy, and time allocation.

Cost Reduction of Automated System of Revenue Collection

Table 1 illustrates the overall mean score on cost reduction due to automated system was 3.3224, meaning that this mean is at the high side of agreement level with implication that automated systems at DART have been perceived to have high contribution toward cost reduction. These findings are interpreted that DART should heavily invest in automating systems and ensure that staff are well trained to master applications of the automated systems and also behavioural change in regard to service provision. These findings are in harmony with those of Kimondio (2024) in Kenya which established that automation of system enhance performance of public transport companies.

Table 1. Cost Reduction of Automated System of Revenue Collection (n = 114)

Attributes	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Changes in expenses or resource utilization since the implementation of the ticketing system	114	1.00	5.00	3.2105	1.29310
Cost reduction has benefited ticketing system	114	1.00	5.00	3.5526	1.24155
I believe that the ticketing system has led to cost savings for the organization	114	1.00	5.00	3.1842	1.28687
I noticed specific cost reduction initiatives been implemented alongside the ticketing system	114	1.00	5.00	3.3421	1.15083
Overall mean score				3.3224	

The mean scores of the perceptions (Table 1) on cost reduction has benefited ticketing system [Mean = 3.5526] and specific cost reduction initiatives been implemented alongside the ticketing system [Mean = 3.3421] were above the overall mean score of 3.3224, suggesting that both variables were perceived in a high side of agreement level, remarking acceptable contribution towards cost reduction. These results suggest that the implementation of the ticketing system has generally been perceived as beneficial in terms of cost reduction, though the degree of perceived impact varies. The findings align with the study by Mwangi and Otieno (2021) which found significant cost reductions due to automated systems in East African cities, the findings of this study are consistent. The study highlights the economic advantages of automation in reducing operational and labor costs. The consistency can be attributed to the similarities in the contexts of urban transit systems in East Africa, where the need for efficient and accurate fare collection is critical.

Further, the mean scores of the perceptions (Table 1) on changes in expenses since the implementation of the ticketing system [Mean = 3.2105] and the belief that automated system has led to cost reduction [Mean = 3.1842] were below the overall mean score of 3.3224, though in reality, their mean score being above 3.0 depict that high side of agreement regarding their contribution toward cost reduction. In this view, both variable are interpreted that they have acceptable contribution toward cost reduction. These findings sound in a similar way with those of Kimondio (2024) in Kenya which established that automation of system enhance performance of public transport companies. The findings support the Diffusion of Innovation Theory, as they demonstrate the adoption of automated systems due to their relative advantage in cost reduction. This aligns with the theory's assertion that innovations are more likely to be adopted if they offer clear benefits over existing practices. The positive perception of cost savings among respondents indicates that the automated ticketing system is viewed as an advantageous innovation, thus facilitating its diffusion within the DART project. The theory aligns with the findings since automated system as technological diffusion has helped to boost revenue collection, meaning that continuous improvement in automating system will result into continuous improvement in revenue at DART.

Revenue Accuracy of Automated System of Revenue Collection

The overall mean score on accuracy of revenue (Table 1) if revenue collection systems are automated was 3.4693, with connotation that if DART fully automates revenue collection systems, there will be maximized likelihood to improve revenue collection since customers will be happy with the system performance due to improved accuracy and reduced errors. These findings are favoured with those of Kimondio (2024) which came out with argument that automated systems favoured the performance of public transport companies in Kenya.

Table 2. Revenue Accuracy of Automated System of Revenue Collection (n = 114)

Attributes	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
The revenue discrepancies or errors while using the automated ticketing system	114	1.00	5.00	3.0877	1.53750
Believe that the automated system ensures precise revenue recording and tracking	114	1.00	5.00	3.9035	1.09681
Automated system provides accuracy on revenue reporting and tracking	114	1.00	5.00	3.4211	1.19656
Automated ticketing system handles data validation and error detection on revenue	114	1.00	5.00	3.4649	1.38372
Overall mean score				3.4693	

Table 2 presents the mean score of 3.9035 about the belief that the automated system ensures precise revenue recording and tracking, this mean score was higher than the average mean score of 3.4693 for all variables. These findings infer that the adoption of automated system by DART has maximized precision on revenue recording and tracking. It is from these findings further interpretation of the findings can be considered on the grounds that DART should strive hard to ensure that automation of systems is continuously embraced, and it is parallel with investment in human capital development who interact with the system on daily operations. These findings coincide with those of Kimondio (2024) in Kenya which argued that the performance of public transport companies increased due to automation of systems.

Though the mean scores of the revenue discrepancies or errors using automated ticketing system [Mean = 3.0877], automated system provides accuracy on revenue reporting and tracking [Mean = 3.4211] and automated ticketing system handles data validation and error detection on revenue transaction [Mean = 3,4649] were below the overall mean score of 3.4693, still they were on a high side of agreement level counted from the neutral point. These findings are interpreted that automation of revenue collection system at DART has helped to minimize errors during ticketing system that consequently improved revenue collection. Further, the findings are interpreted that automation of revenue collection system by DART has helped to increase accuracy on revenue reporting, handling data validation during revenue transactions and consequently has enhanced revenue collection. These findings are consistent with the study by Kamau and Mwendu (2022), which also found that automated fare collection systems improved revenue accuracy by reducing discrepancies and errors. The similarity can be attributed

to the comparable contexts of public transportation systems in Nairobi and Dar es Salaam, where automation enhances financial management and accountability.

The findings support the Diffusion of Innovation Theory by demonstrating that the automated system's relative advantage in ensuring precise revenue recording and tracking promotes its adoption. According to the theory, innovations that offer clear improvements over existing methods are more likely to be embraced. The positive perception of revenue accuracy among respondents indicates the automated system's effectiveness, aligning with the theory's emphasis on the importance of perceived benefits in the diffusion process. The theory also provides a call for DART to continuously invest in automation of system which in the regard to the current study tend to reduce errors in during ticketing, recording and tracking, as the result revenue collection is improved. The theory provides foundation to DART to continue updating automated systems to suit new and emerging technologies and embrace the efforts for human capital development.

Time Allocation of Automated System of Revenue Collection

Table 3 summarizes the overall mean score for time allocation of automated system of revenue collection was 3.3991, inferring that the mean score is on the high level of agreement with implication that automated system has minimized time to serve customers, consequently customers become happy to use DART services. These findings show close coherence with those of Fournier et al. (2024) which pinpointed that automated transport systems were revealed beneficial to improvement of quality of services, reliability and time spent in service delivery.

Table 3. Time Allocation of Automated System of Revenue Collection (n = 114)

Attributes	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Automated ticketing system helps to manage time and prioritize tasks	114	1.00	5.00	3.4737	.70661
It is easy to allocate time efficiently using the automated ticketing system	114	1.00	5.00	3.1667	1.04684
Automated ticketing system effectively optimize time allocation	114	1.00	5.00	3.4912	.82275
I always encountered challenges in determining task priorities within the ticketing system	114	1.00	5.00	3.4649	1.08228
Overall mean score				3.3991	

The means scores summarized in Table 3 for automated ticketing system helps to manage time and prioritize tasks [Mean = 3.4737], automated ticketing system effectively optimize time allocation [Mean = 3.4912] and challenges always encountered in determining task priorities within the ticketing system were higher than the overall mean score of 3.3991, picturing that automated system at DART has played a great role in shortening time allocated to serve a single customer, hence improves level of customer satisfaction. Though the mean score for easy to allocate time efficiently using automated ticketing system [Mean = 3.1667] was lower that the overall mean score of 3.3991 but

still it was on the high side of agreement, presenting the meaning that automated system has resulted into easy of allocating time efficiently which in return result into improved revenue collection. These results align with the study by Ahmed and Njeri (2020), which found that automated fare collection systems significantly improved time efficiency in public transit. The similarities can be attributed to the inherent advantages of automation in streamlining transaction processes and reducing boarding times, thereby enhancing operational efficiency.

The findings support the Diffusion of Innovation theory, which posits that innovations offering clear advantages are more likely to be adopted. The perceived benefits of the automated ticketing system in optimizing time allocation demonstrate its relative advantage, promoting its acceptance among users. This alignment with the theory highlights the importance of effective time management as a key factor in the successful diffusion of automated systems in transit operations. This means that practicability of the Diffusion of Innovation Theory is seen in effective time management which emanates from adopting system automation. It is important to appreciate that when time is effectively and efficiently utilized by DART through automation, the revenue collection consequently will be improved.

Inferential Analysis

Normality Distribution of the Data

The Normal Q-Q plots of cost reduction, revenue accuracy, and time allocation for the automated system of revenue collection in the DART project demonstrate that the data points closely align with the diagonal line.

Figure 1. Normal Q-Q Plot of Cost Reduction, Revenue Accuracy, and Time Allocation of Automated System of Revenue Collection

This alignment suggests that the data for each variable follows a normal distribution. The slight deviations at the tails indicate minor departures from normality, but overall, the linearity of the points confirms the normality assumption. This is important for conducting parametric statistical tests, which assume normal distribution of data, thus

ensuring the reliability and validity of the results in evaluating the automated system's performance.

Test of Normality

Table 4 presents the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests of normality for the cost reduction, revenue accuracy, and time allocation of the automated system of revenue collection.

Table 4. Tests of Normality

	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
Cost Reduction of Automated System of Revenue Collection	.144	114	.000	.951	114	.000
Revenue Accuracy of Automated System of Revenue Collection	.132	114	.000	.962	114	.003
Time Allocation of Automated System of Revenue Collection	.105	114	.003	.974	114	.024
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction						

The results indicate that all three variables have significant p-values (Sig.) less than 0.05 for both tests, suggesting that the data significantly deviates from a normal distribution. Specifically, the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test shows p-values of .000, .000, and .003 for cost reduction, revenue accuracy, and time allocation, respectively, while the Shapiro-Wilk test reports p-values of .000, .003, and .024. These findings imply that the assumption of normality is violated for these datasets, which may affect the choice of subsequent statistical analyses. However, Pallant (2016) pointed out that the significance of Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk is anticipated for large sample sizes, but this circumstance cannot be counted as deviation of data from normal distribution and such results were deemed suitable for t-test in respect to the Kolmogorov-Smirnov and Shapiro-Wilk tests (Mashenene, 2016; Abbasi, 2011).

Correlation Analysis

Table 5 presents the Spearman's rank correlations among total revenue per day, cost reduction, revenue accuracy, and time allocation for the automated system of revenue collection. The results show a significant positive correlation between cost reduction and time allocation ($r = .242$, $p = .009$), indicating that as cost reduction improves, so does time efficiency. Additionally, cost reduction is negatively correlated with revenue accuracy ($r = -.192$, $p = .041$), suggesting a trade-off between these variables. Revenue accuracy and time allocation also exhibit a negative correlation ($r = -.210$, $p = .025$). However, total revenue per day does not significantly correlate with any other variables, implying it operates independently within this context.

Table 5. Correlations Analysis

			Total Revenue in TZS per day	Cost Reduction	Revenue Accuracy	Time Allocation
Spearman's rho	Total Revenue in TZS per day	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	-.105	-.007	.101
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.267	.941	.287
		N	114	114	114	114
	Cost Reduction	Correlation Coefficient	-.105	1.000	-.192*	.242**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.267	.	.041	.009
		N	114	114	114	114
	Revenue Accuracy	Correlation Coefficient	-.007	-.192*	1.000	-.210*
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.941	.041	.	.025
		N	114	114	114	114
	Time Allocation	Correlation Coefficient	.101	.242**	-.210*	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.287	.009	.025	.
		N	114	114	114	114
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).						
**.S Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						

Regression Analysis

Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

Table 6 shows the Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients for the model used in the study. The Chi-square value of 62.531 with 43 degrees of freedom is significant ($p = .027$), indicating that the overall model is statistically significant. This means that the predictors included in the model collectively contribute to explaining the variance in the dependent variable. The significance of the step, block, and model tests confirms that the model provides a good fit to the data and that the inclusion of the predictors enhances the model's explanatory power.

Table 6. Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients

		Chi-square	df	Sig.
Step 1	Step	62.531	43	.027
	Block	62.531	43	.027
	Model	62.531	43	.027

Model Summary

Table 7 provides the Model Summary for the regression analysis with total revenue in TZS per day as the dependent variable. The -2 Log likelihood value of 85.210 indicates the model's fit, where lower values represent a better fit. The Cox & Snell R Square value of .422 and the Nagelkerke R Square value of .581 suggest that the model explains between 42.2% to 58.1% of the variance in total revenue per day. However, the note about estimation terminating at iteration 20 due to reaching the maximum iterations without finding a final solution indicates potential convergence issues, suggesting the model may require refinement or more iterations for a stable solution.

Table 7. Model Summary

Step	-2 Log likelihood	Cox & Snell R Square	Nagelkerke R Square
1	85.210 ^a	.422	.581
a. Estimation terminated at iteration number 20 because maximum iterations have been reached. Final solution cannot be found.			

Binary Logistic Regression Results

Table 8 summarizes the findings that the coefficient of cost reduction was 0.951, positive and statistically significant at $p = 0.012$, meaning that any change in unit of cost reduction will lead to 95.1% rise in revenue collection. These results further are augmented with odds ratio of 2.589 informing that the likelihood of cost reduction to contribute to revenue collection increase was 2.6 times, the contribution which justifiable and suggesting that as cost reduction is exercised, revenue collection is highly improved. These findings consistently match with closely with the findings of Kimondio (2024) which expressed that public transport companies' performance in Kenya improved after systems were automated.

Table 8. Binary logistic regression results (n = 114)

Variables	β	S.E.	Wald	Df	Sig.	Exp(B)
Cost Reduction	.951	.380	6.274	1	.012	2.589
Revenue Accuracy	1.044	.354	8.722	1	.003	2.841
Time Allocation	-1.651	.582	8.036	1	.005	.192
Constant	1.238	2.435	.258	1	.611	3.447
a. Variable(s): Cost Reduction, Revenue Accuracy, Time Allocation.						

Further, Table 8 presents that the coefficient of revenue accuracy was 1.044 with positive and statistically significant effect on revenue collection ($p = 0.003$), indicating that any unit improvement in revenue accuracy will result into increased revenue collection by 104.4%. The findings also are justified with odds ratio of 2.841 which is interpreted that the likelihood of revenue accuracy to contribute to improved revenue collection was 2.8 times. These findings are consistent with the study by Kamau and Mwendu (2022) which presented that automated fare collection systems increased revenue accuracy by reducing discrepancies and errors, subsequently increased revenue collection.

Conversely, Table 8 presents that time allocation was a significant negative predictor ($p = 0.005$) and coefficient of -1.651 , meaning that a unit increase in time allocated for revenue collection will cause a diminish in revenue collection by 165.1% with an odds ratio of $.192$, suggesting that higher time allocation reduces the likelihood of higher revenue. These findings are closely related to those of Fournier et al. (2024) which found that automated transport systems in European Union helped to improve service quality, reliability and time spent in service delivery.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The study aimed to evaluate the impact of automated systems on revenue collection in the DART project, focusing on cost reduction, revenue accuracy, and time allocation. The conclusion drawn from the research findings is that automated system has resulted into improved revenue collection through close loopholes in revenue losses by ensuring there is improved cost reduction, revenue accuracy and minimized time allocated to provide service to a customer. Such results have helped to draw up a conclusion that automated system have been the solution to revenue collection inefficiencies experienced in the previous years for instance a loss of three billion in 2019 due to manual revenue collection system (TRA, 2020). The automated revenue collection system has also eliminated errors that were caused by human, fraud and loss in revenue. For instance, in 2021 due to system outage and resumption to manual revenue collection, DART experienced a revenue loss of 15% (DART, 2021). The findings also lead to draw the conclusion that time allocated to provide services to DART customers as it diminishes depict improved quality of services which result into improved customer satisfaction, repeat purchase and consequently enhanced revenue collection. The overall, the automated systems in the DART project have demonstrated substantial benefits in optimizing cost, accuracy, and time, leading to improved revenue collection.

Recommendations

To enhance revenue collection in the DART project, it is recommended to invest further in optimizing highly sophisticated automated systems that will perform outstandingly and result into cost reduction and improved revenue accuracy through advanced validation algorithms. The DART also should consider streamlining processes to address time allocation inefficiencies during service delivery that consequently will boost level of customer satisfaction and trigger repeat purchase that automatically will improve revenue collection. DART should conduct comprehensive staff training and continuous support regarding mindset and competencies toward usage of automated systems for improved revenue collection. Further, DART should ensure that regular system evaluations and benchmarking against global best practices are taken into practice to obtain valuable insights and make necessary adjustment accordingly. It is further recommended to policymakers including the ministry of Transport and other multisectoral ministries like Ministry of Industry and Trade and others to collaboratively ensure supportive regulations and involvement of stakeholders in feedback discussions in order to foster system acceptance and improvement. These steps will enhance revenue

collection efficiency and overall operational performance, ensuring the financial sustainability of the DART project is achieved.

Further Suggestions for Future Study

Future studies should examine the long-term effects of automated systems on revenue collection and operational efficiency in the DART project using a longitudinal design. Expanding the sample size and incorporating qualitative methods, like interviews, focus group discussions, could provide deeper insights into system inefficiencies and stakeholders' experiences. Comparative studies with other transit systems in different regions could help identify best practices. Additionally, exploring the integration of emerging technologies, such as artificial intelligence and machine learning, may reveal new opportunities for enhancing revenue collection and operational efficiency. Furthermore, consideration in future to include potential mediators or moderators as variables in the conceptual framework to form study variables is recommended. The use of advanced statistical methods in data analysis such as structural modelling or mediation analysis for exploring relationships between variables more deeply is also recommended.

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